

ELEMENTAL DEPTH PROFILING OF THIN LAYERS BY HEAVY-ION ERDA

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Heavy-Ion ERDA (Elastic Recoil Detection Analysis) can be used to characterize thin layers [1]. Absolute concentrations of the chemical elements can be detected as well as the layers' thickness or depth profiles. The ERDA principle is based on the classical Rutherford scattering theory. A sample is irradiated with a heavy ion beam (e.g. Au); atoms of the sample are recoiled and detected with a spectrometer (Figure 1).

Figure 1: ERDA principle. A sample is irradiated with ions (e.g. Au ions with a kinetic energy of 350 MeV). The time-of-flight (TOF) and the energy of the recoiled atoms are measured.

The expected yields for the given conditions can be calculated exactly (equation 1).

$$\frac{d\sigma_r}{d\Omega} = \left(\frac{Z_p Z_r e^2}{2E_p} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M_p + M_r}{M_r} \right)^2 \frac{1}{\cos^3 \phi} \quad (1)$$

Equation 1: The differential cross section $d_r d$ (probability of a scattering process) can be calculated exactly for a given scattering angle ϕ . Z_p and Z_r are the element numbers of projectile and recoiled atom, respectively, M_p and M_r the mass numbers, E_p is the energy of the projectile.

Therefore, ERDA is a standard-free method. Absolute concentrations can be determined for all detected chemical elements simultaneously.

The ERDA spectrometer (Figure 2) at the Hahn-Meitner-Institut (HMI) [2] is placed in a high-vacuum chamber. Before hitting a semiconductor energy detector, each recoil passes a pair of very thin foils. The electrons resulting from ionization processes in the foils are amplified by channel-plate detectors enabling the generation of short (<0.5 ns) start and stop signals for the time-of-flight (TOF) measurement. Typical flight times for the distance between the foils (120 cm) are 10 to 100 ns. Coincident energy- and TOF-signals are stored event-by-event.

Figure 2: Sketch of the ERDA-TOF setup at the HMI. The atoms which are recoiled from the sample cross two time detectors (TOF measurement) before hitting a semiconductor detector (energy measurement).

If the individual TOF of each detected atom is plotted versus its energy, the result is a graph in which each branch corresponds to a specific atomic mass (Figure 3). Moreover, the energetic position on the branch corresponds to a specific energy loss in the sample, which can be attributed to the depth from which the scattered atom is originating.

Figure 3: The depth distribution of an element in the sample corresponds to an energy distribution in the scatterplot. Atoms which are recoiled from a position near the surface of the sample have high energies; atoms which are originating from a deeper position lose energy while crossing the sample.

As an example, figure 4 shows the TOF vs. energy plot of an ERDA measurement of a multilayer structure for a solar cell (glass/Mo/Cu,In,Ga,S,Se/Zn,Se,I). The mass resolution is sufficient to enable the distinction of the isotopes of an element. In the given example, although the Zn signal is overlapping with the Cu signal, a profiling of Zn can be performed because the isotope Zn-68 can be separated from the Cu signal.

Figure 4: A scatterplot (energy vs. TOF) from the irradiation of a solar cell precursor. For technical reasons, the TOF is subtracted from a constant delay time t_0 .

To obtain quantitative data from a measurement, the branches are individually selected and projected into 1-dimensional energy spectra (Figure 5). These spectra are fitted using a simulation code based on the physical principles of classical Coulomb scattering. Mass and energy of the projectile and the number of projectiles are known; the observables are mass, energy and number of the detected atoms for a given scattering angle. The code takes into account semi-empirical data concerning the energy loss of ions in matter. Layer thicknesses and elemental concentrations are used as free parameters. They are adjusted such that the resulting simulated spectra are consistent with the measurement.

Figure 5: A branch, corresponding to a specific mass, e.g. oxygen, can be cut out and projected onto the energy scale. The resulting energy spectrum is fitted using a simulation code. Finally, the energy scale can be converted into a depth scale.

As a final result, the structure of the sample can be reconstructed (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Reconstructed depth profiles of B, C, N, O, Si, Cl and Ti. The sample is a multilayer structure of Si (containing Cl) / TiN (containing O) / glass (Si,O,B).

Currently, one of the main subjects of the ERDA measurements is the investigation of experimental solar cells. Typical applications are

- depth profiling of all chemical elements (including H) with a depth resolution of 20 nm near the surface (enlarging with depth) up to a maximum layer thickness of about 3 μm .

- determination of areal densities (thicknesses) from monolayers up to 1-3 μm thick films.

- determination of the stoichiometry and impurities of thin layers.

- investigation of diffusion processes on interfaces.

- calibration of analytical standard techniques, e.g. Infrared Spectroscopy and Secondary Ion Mass Spectroscopy.

The sensitivity is about 10 ppm under appropriate conditions.

References

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